

Investigating the Effects of Technology Adoption on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) In Zambia: A Case Study of Kitwe District

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 13th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Technology Adoption SMEs Performance SMEs Revenue SMEs Operational Cost Kitwe Zambia</p>	<p>This study examined the effect of technology adoption on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Kitwe town. This paper was motivated by the three specific objectives; to determine the extent to which technology has been adopted by SMEs; assess how technology adoption affects SME revenue; and to evaluate how technology adoption influences operational costs among SMEs in Kitwe town. Quantitative approach was adopted, with 50 different businesses selected through purposive random sampling. The results show that at least 70% of SMEs have adopted at least one form of technology in their businesses and chi-square test yielded the significant distribution with test of independence proving positive ($\chi^2=15.67$, $p=0.003$) which shows statistically significant association between the size of the SMEs and the level of technology. The results on the effect of technology on SMEs revenue, regression analysis showed a positive coefficient (0.25, $p=0.002$) indicating that for every unit increase in technology adoption, SMEs revenue increases by an average of 25% and these results show that it is statically significant. The regression function thus gave a positive slope in the function indicating a positive relationship with high causality influence. The effect of technology influence on operational costs among SMEs showed an inverse relationship tested significant at 50, t-test output ($t=4.56$, $p=0.001$) which is statistically significant. The slope was found to have a value of -7 factor reduction in operational costs for every unit of technology incorporated in the business. This was a remarkable indicator showing that there is a reduction in operational costs to a tune of 7 times after technology adoption of a unit. Indeed, technology adoption leads to lower operational costs. This study further found that over 74% of businesses were able to adopt technology without extreme financial strain, while a smaller portion faced higher costs that may have limited the scale or speed of adoption. Overall, the data suggests that there is positive correlation between technology adoption and business performance however this comes with its own bigger and minor challenges depending on the size and type of the firm of the business. The study recommends expanding technology integration, financial support and affordability, encourages awareness and knowledge sharing as well as capacity building and skills. The government needs to invest in research and development and reward innovation for those SMEs adopting and devising new technologies.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Hashim (2011) is among the many scholars who asserted that Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are a vital component in economic development. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are widely known as the key of global economies, representing about 90% of all businesses, providing more than 70% of total employment, and contributing nearly 50% to global GDP (United Nations 2024; International Finance Corporation, 2024). SMEs are instrumental in driving poverty reduction and inclusive economic growth by generating most new jobs and sustaining local livelihoods worldwide (International Labour Organization, 2024; McKinsey & Company, 2024). In Africa, SMEs constitute over 90% of businesses and account for about 80% of employment while contributing roughly one-third to non-hydrocarbon GDP, demonstrating their central role in economic

development (African Development Bank, 2025. International Monetary Fund, 2025). Moreover, SMEs promote innovation, local value-chain integration, and industrial diversification by strengthening linkages with larger firms and facilitating formalization (IFC, 2021). However, access to finance remains a major constraint, with the global MSME financing gap estimated between US\$4.5 and US\$5.7 trillion annually (World Bank, 2024). Technology is a key pusher of modern economic growth, fostering productivity, innovation, and competitiveness across global economies (World Bank, 2024; United Nations [UN], 2024). The digital economy contributes about 15.5% to global GDP and is expanding 2.5 times faster than total world GDP (International Monetary Fund, 2025).

1.2 Problem Statement

Mwika (2022) **strongly** supported that ICT adoption has been widely associated with improved efficiency, innovation, and profitability, SMEs in developing countries, including Zambia, continue to exhibit reluctance in adopting these technologies. This reluctance undermines their ability to participate effectively in the global digital economy. Several studies have shown that factors such as lack of ICT knowledge, high costs of implementation, and perceptions of complexity discourage SMEs from embracing technological solutions (Gono, Harindranath & Özcan, 2016; Kamutuezu, Winschiers-Theophilus, & Peters, 2021). Moreover, even where technologies are available, many SMEs struggle to realize tangible benefits due to poor integration with existing business models and limited government support (Mustapha et al., 2022). Consequently, understanding the primary reasons behind this reluctance is essential for developing strategic interventions that promote ICT-driven growth in the SME sector.

1.3 Research Objective

1.3.1 General Objectives

The study aims to examine the effect of technology adoption on the performance of SMEs, focusing on factors contributing to reluctance in ICT adoption. The specific objectives are to:

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- To determine the extent to which technology has been adopted by SMEs.
- To assess how technology adoption affects SME revenue.
- To evaluate how technology adoption influences operational costs among SMEs.

1.4 Research Questions

- To what extent have SMEs adopted ICT in their operations?
- How does ICT adoption affect SME revenue generation?
- What impact does ICT adoption have on SME operational costs?

1.5 Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory, which explained user behavior and organizational decision-making regarding the adoption of new technologies (Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, 1989; Rogers, 2003). TAM focused on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as the primary determinants of technology acceptance. According to this model, the more an individual believes that using a technology will improve job performance and is easy to use, the higher the likelihood of adoption. Conversely,

These theories were suitable for this study because they provide a dual perspective on technology adoption. TAM allowed the study to assess individual-level determinants, particularly owner-manager attitudes, perceptions, and intentions regarding ICT adoption. DOI provided a broader organizational and environmental perspective, highlighting how innovation characteristics and social networks affect adoption decisions. By integrating both models, the study was able to capture the internal cognitive factors and external organizational influences that shape ICT adoption in SMEs.

1.6 Conceptual framework

Below is the figure for conceptual framework that shows the variables under the investigation.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Technology adoption represents the independent variable that influences the dependent variables and in this case these variables include; income generation, extent of technology adoption and operational costs.

1.7 Significance of the Study

This study will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on ICT adoption by providing insights specific to SMEs in developing countries, particularly within the Zambian context. While much of the existing literature has focused on large corporations or SMEs in developed economies, there remains limited understanding of how small enterprises in resource-constrained environments perceive, adopt, and utilize digital technologies. By addressing this gap, the study will enhance understanding of how ICT can be leveraged to improve productivity, competitiveness, and sustainability among SMEs operating in developing economies. A deeper understanding of the barriers and enablers of ICT adoption will provide valuable input for policymakers, development agencies, and business owners. Development agencies will align their programs toward capacity building, infrastructure support, and access to affordable financing for technology investment. Likewise, SME owners and managers will gain practical insights into how technology can be integrated into their operations to improve efficiency and profitability. Lastly, the study will generate practical recommendations aimed at improving ICT awareness and digital literacy among SME operators.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Extent of ICT Adoption among SMEs

Porter and Heppelmann (2014), stated that the embracing of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) has become a key driver of modernization, competitiveness, and business growth. Across both developed and developing economies, ICT enables firms to streamline operations, expand market access, and improve decision-making processes this is postulated by (Bharadwaj et al., 2013) and (Zhu & Kraemer, 2005). However, argues that the extent to which SMEs have adopted ICT differs considerably depending on contextual, economic, and institutional factors (Molla & Licker, 2005).

Globally, emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, mobile banking, and e-commerce are reshaping business operations (Udo et al., 2024; Dlamini and Botha, 2024). In developing economies, particularly in Africa, SMEs often adopt less sophisticated technologies such as mobile phones, social media, and basic e-commerce platforms due to affordability and ease of use (Naatu, Selormey & Naatu, 2024; Agboh, 2015). More advanced innovations like AI, blockchain, and big data analytics remain underutilized because of high costs, limited technical expertise, and weak digital infrastructure (Oduro, 2020).

Evidence from Ghana's National Entrepreneurial and Innovation Programme (NEIP) shows that adoption of advanced technologies remains very low, with only 2.11% of SMEs using AI-based systems compared to over 60% using mobile banking and social media (Naatu et al., 2024). These findings suggest that SMEs are still at an early stage of ICT maturity, focusing on affordable and practical tools that directly support day-to-day business operations. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory help explain the varying degrees of ICT adoption. According to these frameworks, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and social influence significantly shape SME decisions to adopt ICT (Asante Boakye et al., 2023; Krah et al., 2024). Krah et al. (2024) found that perceived convenience drives FinTech adoption among Ghanaian SMEs, while Atta-Ankomah (2024) reported that mobile money usage has diversified employment across sectors such as agriculture and services.

Firm-specific factors also play a role. Adoption levels tend to be higher among larger firms with greater financial capacity, skilled personnel, and managerial competence (Agboh, 2015; Shahadat, Khan and Rahman, 2023). Smaller firms, on the other hand, rely mainly on mobile applications and social media for marketing and communication due to limited absorptive capacity and capital (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Arendt, 2008). Infrastructure and the policy environment further influence ICT adoption rates. Comparative studies show that SMEs in countries with reliable internet connectivity, supportive digital policies, and structured training programs experience higher ICT penetration (Udo et al., 2024; OECD, 2023). Conversely, in developing contexts, barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, low digital literacy, and limited government support remain significant challenges (Ewuga et al., 2023; Mapeshoane and Pather, 2016).

Despite these barriers, ICT continues to transform SME operations in meaningful ways. Digital tools and e-commerce platforms have become essential for improving efficiency, reaching new markets, and ensuring resilience during global disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Mishrif and Khan, 2023; Deloitte, 2024). Studies also report that SMEs leveraging digital tools experience enhanced customer engagement, productivity, and revenue growth (Elbeltagi et al., 2013; Müller, Buliga & Voigt, 2018).

The extent of ICT adoption among SMEs remains uneven yet steadily improving. Adoption is strongest for cost-effective, user-friendly technologies such as mobile banking, social media, and e-commerce, while complex systems like AI and big data analytics are still emerging. To accelerate ICT diffusion, governments and development partners must prioritize affordable digital infrastructure, digital literacy initiatives, and policy incentives that align with SME realities in developing economies.

2.2 Impact of ICT Adoption on SME Operational Costs

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are increasingly recognizing the strategic importance of information and communication technology (ICT) in enhancing operational efficiency and overall business performance (Mishrif & Khan, 2023). ICT serves not only as a cost-reduction and automation tool but also as a transformative force that reshapes competitiveness within the global business landscape (Porter, 2001). Through technologies such as e-commerce, digital payment systems, enterprise resource planning (ERP), mobile applications, social media, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence, SMEs are improving their productivity and lowering operational costs (MacGregor & Vrazalic, 2005; Sultan, 2011; Khan et al., 2023).

The integration of ICT into daily business activities enables SMEs to streamline processes, enhance information flow, and reduce administrative burdens. For instance, e-commerce systems make purchasing faster and cheaper, while broadening market reach both locally and internationally (Indrayanto et al., 2024; Lane et al., 2004). ERP systems merge departmental data, improving information accessibility and supporting efficient decision-making (Olsen & Sætre, 2007a). Similarly, mobile technology enhances communication, enables real-time data collection, and boosts coordination among staff (Bankosz & Kerins, 2014).

Social media has also become a cost-effective marketing platform, allowing SMEs to build brand reputation, strengthen customer trust, and minimize expenses associated with traditional advertising (Durkin et al., 2013; Sulasih et al., 2023). Digital payment systems simplify transactions, reducing the cost and time associated with cash handling (Küster et al., 2016). Moreover, cloud computing and blockchain technologies enable cost flexibility by reducing hardware investments and improving data security (Sultan, 2011; Khan et al., 2023). Collectively, these technologies contribute to lowering transaction costs, optimizing resource use, and improving responsiveness to market changes.

Empirical evidence indicates that SMEs with strong ICT capabilities tend to achieve better financial outcomes and operational efficiency compared to firms with weaker ICT integration (Elbeltagi et al., 2013). Nevertheless, ICT adoption in SMEs particularly in developing countries remains limited due to financial, technical, and organizational barriers (Shahadat et al., 2023; Arendt, 2008). Studies show that while large corporations benefit significantly from ICT-driven cost savings, smaller firms often lack the infrastructure and managerial capacity to fully exploit these technologies (Cragg & King, 1993; Chege et al., 2020).

(OECD, 2021), points out that the cost implications of ICT adoption extend beyond direct expenses such as system installation and training. (World Bank, 2022) and (Gono et al., 2016), agrees that in the long term, ICT helps SMEs reduce costs associated with inventory management, communication, and customer service. (UNCTAD, 2021), also shares that ICT minimizes operational redundancies by integrating workflows and automating repetitive tasks. However, in developing economies, the cost-saving potential of ICT is sometimes undermined by inconsistent internet connectivity, lack of technical expertise, and inadequate digital literacy (Kurnia et al., 2015; Mapeshoane & Pather, 2016).

Despite these challenges, SMEs that strategically invest in ICT have reported significant improvements in operational efficiency, market competitiveness, and customer satisfaction (Azam, 2015; Müller et al., 2018). ICT adoption not only reduces day-to-day operating costs but also fosters innovation and resilience, enabling small firms to adapt quickly to market disruptions such as those witnessed during the COVID-19 pandemic (Mishrif & Khan, 2023; Meramveliotakis & Manioudis, 2021).

Therefore, while the initial costs of ICT adoption may seem prohibitive for many SMEs, the long-term benefits such as cost efficiency, enhanced productivity, and improved market positioning outweigh the short-term financial burden. This underscores the need for supportive policies, capacity-building initiatives, and affordable digital infrastructure to enable SMEs, especially in developing countries, to fully harness the cost-saving potential of ICT.

2.3 Research Gaps

Despite extensive global research on ICT and SME performance, notable gaps remained, especially in developing countries such as Zambia. In terms of the extent of ICT adoption, most existing studies provided only a general overview of ICT usage without comprehensively measuring the depth of adoption in terms of technological sophistication, usage intensity, or integration across various business functions (Chinomona & Sandada 2018), Mutula and van Brakel (2019), and Muriithi (2017) agreed and noted that there was limited empirical evidence on which specific ICT tools such as artificial intelligence (AI), e-commerce, enterprise resource planning (ERP), or mobile applications were most prevalent among Zambian SMEs and how deeply these tools were embedded in their daily operations, Asare et al. (2021)

Regarding ICT and revenue generation, although literature consistently linked ICT adoption with improved revenue and market expansion (Taruté & Gatautis, 2014; Ab Wahab et al., 2020), there was a scarcity of context-specific studies quantifying this relationship in developing economies. Most studies stopped at correlational analysis without explaining the mechanisms through which ICT translated into financial gains, such as customer retention, market diversification, or enhanced production efficiency. In relation to ICT and operational costs, research on cost reduction mainly emphasized general operational efficiency but lacked detailed analysis of cost structures specific to SMEs. Empirical data on how ICT affected direct and indirect costs such as communication, inventory, or labor costs within small businesses were limited. Furthermore, few studies addressed the paradox of high initial ICT investment versus long-term cost savings in resource-constrained environments.

From a contextual and policy perspective, much of the available evidence originated from countries such as Ghana, Nigeria, and Kenya, leaving a clear contextual gap regarding Zambia's SME landscape. Osei and Abenyin (2016) and Quartey et al. (2017), there was limited exploration of how local infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, and digital literacy influenced ICT adoption outcomes. Additionally, few comparative studies evaluated differences in ICT adoption across urban and rural SMEs.

There was a clear need for empirical, context-specific research that examined the extent, economic impact, and cost implications of ICT adoption among SMEs in Zambia. Meyer and de Villiers (2017) Addressing these gaps would not only contribute to academic literature but also provide evidence-based insights for policymakers and development practitioners seeking to enhance SME performance through digital transformation. Deloitte (2021), GSMA (2019), and PwC (2020), emphasize and reinforce that there is a growing evidence that shows that SMEs are improving due to the insights from the digital improvement.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive case study design. A case study approach was particularly suited for exploring contemporary phenomena within real-life contexts (Yin, 2014). In this case, the context involved indigenous SMEs in the Kitwe. The descriptive design enabled the researcher to collect both qualitative and quantitative data, providing a comprehensive understanding of ICT

application and its organizational outcomes. This method facilitated the exploration of prevailing practices, challenges, and stakeholder perspectives on ICT adoption and implementation.

3.2 Study Area

The research was conducted in Kitwe central business area to be specific, this town is a commercial and industrial hub in the Copperbelt Province of Zambia. Kitwe hosts a growing number of indigenous SMEs, making it a suitable location for analyzing ICT effectiveness in local business operations. The setting provided relevant insights into both the technological and organizational contexts in which ICT systems were deployed.

3.3 Target Population

The target population for this study comprised few small and medium scale business from indigenous SMEs in Kitwe. This included top management such as directors and senior executives, middle management such as department heads and data analysts, and lower-level staff including clerks and customer service agents

3.4 Sampling Design

A sampling technique was employed to select units of the sample (Bryman, 2008), A study used a combined design stratified, purposive simple random sampling strategy was employed to ensure a representative and relevant selection of respondents. This approach allowed for both breadth and depth in the study sample, combining the strengths of probability and non-probability sampling techniques.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

Given the relatively small population size, a census approach was employed by attempting to include all 50 individuals in the sample. This allowed for a comprehensive and in-depth analysis without the statistical error introduced by sub-sampling.

3.6 Data Collection Instruments

Primary data were collected using a combination of structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaires contained closed-ended questions to facilitate quantitative analysis, as well as open-ended questions to capture qualitative insights. The questionnaire sections were aligned with the research objectives, including background information, ICT usage, data management practices, and strategic decision-making. Interviews were conducted with a subset of respondents, particularly from top and middle management, to gather detailed perspectives on ICT system challenges and benefits.

3.7 Data Collection

This study used a primary data for analysis which the researcher administered through structured and semi-questionnaires and conducted the interviews to ensure consistency in the data collection process and to clarify any ambiguities that would arise during participation.

3.8 Data Analysis

Collected data were coded and entered into Stata for analysis. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequencies, and mean scores summarized responses. Qualitative data from open-ended questions and interviews were analyzed thematically to identify recurring patterns and insights. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests, were used to explore relationships between variables, for example between ICT use and decision-making effectiveness. Results were presented using tables, graphs, and charts for clarity.

3.9 Triangulation

To enhance validity and reliability, methodological triangulation was employed by integrating multiple data collection methods, data sources, and data types. Questionnaires provided standardized data for statistical analysis, while interviews offered rich, narrative explanations that uncovered deeper insights.

Data were drawn from multiple management levels top, middle, and lower to ensure a well-rounded representation of views and experiences related to ICT implementation and usage. This combination of quantitative data (such as frequency of ICT tool usage, training received, or decision-making efficiency) with qualitative data (perceived challenges, organizational attitudes, and behavioral responses) ensured a comprehensive exploration of both measurable outcomes and intangible factors influencing ICT adoption, such as organizational culture, leadership support, and digital readiness.

3.10 Limitations of the Study

The study faced several limitations. Access to sensitive operational data was sometimes restricted due to confidentiality concerns. Differences in digital literacy levels among respondents affected their understanding of ICT-related questions. Financial and logistical constraints also limited the scope and depth of data collection. The researcher mitigated these challenges by ensuring clear communication, implementing confidentiality agreements, and scheduling data collection efficiently.

3.11 Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles were strictly observed throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were assured of their anonymity and the confidentiality of their responses. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were

allowed to withdraw at any time without penalty. Ethical approval and permission were sought from relevant institutional authorities prior to data collection.

4. Data Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Presentation of Results Based on the demographics of Respondents.

4.1.1 Gender distribution

Below the figure shows the gender distribution of the respondents who took part in the survey

Figure 2: Gender Distribution

The distribution for gender shows that this paper captured 31 respondents representing 62% of male headed business while 19 respondents representing 38% of female headed business

4.1.2 Level of Education Distribution

The figure below shows the distribution of the level of education of the respondents who took part in the survey.

Figure 2: Highest Level of Education

The figure above represents different categories on the level of education who took part in the survey. Starting with the smallest representation of 5 (10%) who answered have not been to school, followed by those who confirmed that their high level of education is primary education stands at 8 (16%), while 12 (24%) shows secondary as their level of education and the highest covered in this survey is 25(50%) indication that at least half of the sample size have a tertiary education. This distribution indicates that most individuals who are running business 95% have at least primary education attached to their businesses.

4.1.3 Types of business distribution

The survey results on the type of business conducted by respondents is shown below in the figures which highlights a fairly balanced distribution across the four main categories.

Figure 3; Type of Business

Out of 50 respondents, 12 (24%) operate in Manufacturing, 13 (26%) in Retail, 13 (26%) in Services, and 12 (24%) in Agriculture. Retail and Services together account for just over half of the respondents (52%), suggesting that a significant portion of the businesses may be more engaged with customer-facing and technology-driven activities, such as online sales or digital marketing. The cumulative distribution shows that by the second category (Retail), half of the respondents are already accounted for, and by the third category (Services), 76% are included, highlighting the proportional representation of each sector.

4.1.4 Duration of business operation

The figure below shows the results on the duration of business operations distribution which indicate that a majority of the respondents are relatively young enterprises.

Figure 4 Years in business

Out of 50 businesses, 5 (10%) have been in operation for less than one year, 20 (40%) for 1–5 years, 17 (34%) for 5–7 years, and 8 (16%) have been operating for more than 10 years. This distribution shows that most businesses fall within the early to mid-stage of development, with the 1–5 years and 5–7 years categories together accounting for 74% of respondents.

4.1.5 Monthly Revenue

The figure below shows the distribution on the approximate monthly revenue for the business or respondent engaged during the survey.

Figure 5 Monthly Revenue

These results on monthly revenue above show a diverse range of business earnings among respondents. Out of 50 businesses, 12 (24%) reported earning less than 50,000, 7 (14%) reported exactly 50,000, 18 (36%) earned between 50,000 and 100,000, and 13 (26%) reported revenues above 100,000. This distribution indicates that while a substantial proportion of businesses (36%) earn moderate revenue, there is also a significant number of high-earning enterprises (26%) as well as smaller-scale businesses (38% earning 50,000 or below).

4.2 Presentation of Results Based on the Extent of ICT Adoption among SMEs

4.2.1 Has your business adopted any technology in the past 3 years?

The survey results on the adoption of new technology in the past three years indicate that a majority of businesses have embraced recent technological innovations

Figure 6 Technology Adoption

Out of 50 respondents, 31 businesses (62%) reported adopting new technology, 12 (24%) had not adopted any, and 7 (14%) were not sure. This suggests that most businesses are actively updating their technological capabilities

4.2.2 In what ways are you using technology in your business?

Below is the figure that shows different ways businesses are using technology.

Figure 7 Using Technology In Your Business

Out of 50 respondents, 12 businesses (24%) use technology for online advertising, 13 (26%) for online sales, 12 (24%) for co-piloting, and 13 (26%) for processing payments. This distribution shows that businesses are integrating technology into multiple aspects of their operations rather than focusing on a single function

4.2.4 What areas of your business use technology most?

The survey results on the areas of business that use technology most show a clear focus on core operational functions.

Figure 8; Areas in Business Using Technology

Out of 50 respondents, 20 businesses (40%) use technology primarily in marketing and sales, 13 (26%) in accounting and finance, 12 (24%) in inventory management, and 5 (10%) in customer service. This indicates that technology adoption is concentrated in revenue-generating and operational efficiency areas, with marketing and sales being the leading focus.

4.2.5 Regression Analysis On Objective One

The different SMEs have different technology orientation and the higher the technology based processes the higher the chances of embracing technology. The regression reveals that over 93% of the causality in techno adoption is caused by the type of business of the SME (group). See table 1 below and confirm that;

The function was estimated to be as below;

$$T = 1.72 + 0.996Tg$$

Where T is the level of technology in the processes and 1.72 is the interception and the function sustained a slope of 0.996. which shows that while the level of technology is determined by the type of techno SME group (Tg) the relationship is linear with sensitivity of almost one on one.

Table 1: Test for Significance

reg tech_adopt tech_group

tech_adopt	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Int]
tech_group	.9960	.0365	27.27	0.000	.9227 1.0693
_cons	1.7200	.0258	66.67	0.000	1.6680 1.7720

R-squared = 0.938

The coefficient 0.996 means high-adoption SMEs score 0.996 points higher on technology adoption. p < .001 this points out that it is statistically significant.

R² = 0.938 tech group explains 93.8% of the variation in tech adoption.

SMEs differ strongly in their technology adoption level, and tech adoption is significantly higher among high-tech SMEs.

4.3 Presentation of Results Based on how technology adoption affects SME revenue

4.3.1 since adopting technology, by how much has your sales revenue increased by?

The survey results on the impact of technology adoption on sales revenue indicate that technology has positively influenced business earnings for most respondents.

Figure.9; sales increase since adopting technology

Out of 50 businesses, 12 (24%) reported a revenue increase of less than 30%, 25 (50%) experienced an increase between 30% and 50%, and 13 (26%) saw revenue grow by more than 75%. This shows that half of the businesses achieved moderate gains, while a notable portion (26%) experienced substantial improvements in sales, demonstrating the potential of technology to drive business growth.

4.3.5 Overall, what impact has technology had on your business revenue?

The survey results on the overall impact of technology on business revenue indicate that most businesses have benefited from digital tools.

Figure 10; overall impact of technology on business revenue

From the 50 respondents, 20 (40%) reported a strong positive impact, 18 (36%) experienced a moderate positive impact, and 12 (24%) observed no impact. This shows that 76% of businesses have seen at least some improvement in revenue due to technology, highlighting its role in enhancing business performance and growth.

4.3.6 Statistical testing; Regression analysis

There is a positive relationship between levels of technology adoption and the revenue of the SME estimated to the marginal propensity of 15.45. The function was estimated to be as below;

$$R = 21.39 + 15.45T$$

Where R is the revenue and T is the level of technology in the processes and 21.39 is the intercept and the function sustained a slope of 15.45.

Table 2: Technology and Revenue

reg revenue tech_adopt

variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Int]
tech adopt	15.45	0.95	16.26	0.000	13.53 17.36
_cons	21.39	2.04	10.49	0.000	17.28 25.50

R-squared = 0.844

Coefficient 15.45, this means that each 1-unit increase in technology adoption increases revenue by 15.45 units (K'000). $p < 0.001$ =highly significant. $R^2 = 0.844$ tech adoption explains 84.4% of revenue differences.

Lastly, Technology adoption has a strong and significant positive effect on SME revenue.

Higher adopters earn far more revenue.

4.4 Presentation of Results Based on what impact does ICT adoption have on SME operational costs?

4.4.1 Has technology reduced your business's operational costs (e.g paperwork, communication)?

The survey results on the effect of technology on operational costs indicate that digital tools have contributed to cost reduction for most businesses.

Figure 11; Has technology reduced business operational costs?

Out of 50 respondents, 20 (40%) reported that technology significantly reduced operational costs, 18 (36%) said it reduced costs slightly, and 12 (24%) indicated no reduction. This shows that 76% of businesses have experienced some level of cost savings through technology, highlighting its importance in improving efficiency, reducing paperwork, and streamlining communication.

4.4.2 Was the initial cost of adopting technology affordable for your business?

The survey results on the affordability of the initial cost of adopting technology indicate that most businesses found it manageable.

Figure 12 Was the initial cost of adopting technology for your business ?

Out of 50 respondents, 12 businesses (24%) reported that the cost was very affordable, 25 (50%) said it was somehow affordable, and 13 (26%) considered it expensive. This shows that 74% of businesses were able to adopt technology without extreme financial strain, while a smaller portion faced higher costs that may have limited the scale or speed of adoption.

4.4.3 Overall, What Is Your View of Technology effect On Business Costs

The survey results on the overall effect of technology on business costs indicate that most respondents perceive a positive impact.

Figure 13; overall, what is your view of technology’s effect on business costs?

Out of 50 businesses, 20 (40%) reported that technology significantly reduces costs, 18 (36%) indicated it slightly reduces costs, and 12 (24%) observed no effect. This shows that 76% of businesses experience some level of cost reduction due to technology, highlighting its role in improving operational efficiency and resource management.

4.4.4 Significant Test: Regression for Objective 3 “Evaluate how technology adoption influences operational costs among SMEs”

The results showed that there is a negative relationship between the level of technology adoption and the operational costs of the firm. The function was estimated to be as below;

$$OC = 52.72 - 7.69T$$

Where OC is the operational cost and T is the level of technology in the processes and 52.72 is the intercept and the function sustained a slope of -7.69 implying an inverse relationship between factors.

Table 3: Effect of Technology on Operation Cost

reg op_cost tech_adopt

op_cost	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Int]
tech_adopt	-7.69	0.55	-13.98	0.000	-8.80 -6.58
_cons	52.72	1.19	44.28	0.000	50.32 55.12

R-squared = 0.806

Coefficient -7.69, Each 1-unit increase in technology adoption reduces operational costs by 7.69 units (K'000).

p < .001, shows a strongly statistically significant figure.

R² = 0.806, tech adoption explains 80.6% of variation in operational costs.

In nutshell, Technology adoption significantly reduces operational costs among SMEs.

High-tech SMEs operate more efficiently and spend less.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

- High ICT Adoption Among SMEs: Most of SMEs (62%) have adopted new technologies in the past three years, with usage focused in marketing, sales, accounting, and inventory management. Regression analysis confirms that high-tech SMEs score significantly higher in adoption, with 93.8% of variation explained by tech group differences, showing strong disparities between adopters and non-adopters.
- Technology Drives Revenue Growth: 76% of SMEs reported revenue improvements after adopting ICT, with 26% experiencing substantial gains above 75%. Regression results show that each unit increase in technology adoption raises revenue by 15.45 K'000, explaining 84.4% of revenue variation. This highlights ICT as a critical driver of SME growth and competitiveness.
- Technology Reduces Operational Costs: 76% of SMEs experienced cost savings, mainly through reduced paperwork, streamlined communication, and improved efficiency. Regression analysis shows that each unit increase in ICT adoption reduces operational costs by 7.69, explaining 80.6% of cost variation. This confirms ICT adoption as a powerful tool for efficiency and sustainability

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 For Business Owners And Policy Makers

To start with the business owners this paper recommends the following

- Expand ICT Use Beyond Core Functions: While most SMEs use ICT in marketing and sales, owners should integrate digital tools into customer service, supply chain, and decision-making processes to maximize efficiency and competitiveness.
- Invest in Staff Training and Digital Skills: To fully leverage ICT, SMEs should prioritize employee training in digital tools, ensuring that technological investments translate into productivity gains and revenue growth.
- Adopt Scalable and Affordable ICT Solutions: SMEs should seek cost-effective, cloud-based, and modular ICT systems that minimize upfront costs while allowing gradual expansion as the business grows.

5.2.2 For Policy Makers

- For policy makers this paper recommends the following to the policy maker to facilitate and create an enabling environment for business society
- Provide Financial Incentives and Subsidies, introduce tax breaks, grants, or low-interest loans to reduce the burden of initial ICT adoption costs, especially for the 26% of SMEs that found adoption expensive.
- Establish ICT Training and Support Programs, Governments and agencies should create SME-focused digital literacy programs, offering workshops, mentorship, and technical support to strengthen ICT integration across industries. Especially for 24% that is rarely using technology in their businesses.
- Promote Digital Infrastructure and Accessibility, expand affordable internet access, digital payment systems, and e-commerce platforms to ensure SMEs—especially in rural or underserved areas—can adopt and benefit from ICT effectively.
- The government needs to invest in research and development and reward innovation for those SMEs adopting and devising new technologies.

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